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Genes that distinguish luminal and non-luminal subtypes in breast cancer.

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We used transcriptomics to precisely distinguish and identify here defining components of the luminal and non-luminal (basal-like or HER2+ subtype) breast cancer gene expression programs.

1 Results

2
3 Immune system: genes that appear to be important for cancer defense because they are silenced,

4 BIVM in breast cancer by subtype

5 HLA class II specific receptor by subtype: hla-dra

6 B2m

7 Lypd3

8 Lym2

9 Ifi2711

10 HM13

11 IRF6

12 Class I is reduced or silenced in HER2/basal cancers (or much higher in luminal A/B: check) Including HLA-F, G, J and A. HLA-E was equivalent between subtypes

13 Class II is Restricted to HLA-DRA and HLA-DQA1, DNA, DPA1, DMB1

14 MR1 is significantly higher in luminal A/B

15 Growth factors.

16 Luminal

17 IGF1 and IGF1R was enriched in luminal A and luminal B breast cancers, as was ERBB4.

18 PDGFD

19 PDGFB

20 RERG

21 FGFR1

22 HDGF

23 HDGFRP

24 Igfbp4, and IGFBP2/5/6/7 were all activated in the luminal subtype.

25 Basal and HER2

26 EGFR

27 HDGF

28 VEGF-A

OGFRL1

Ligands shared:

Gas5

Leptin

Ogfr

Tnfsf13

1 Receptors equivalently expressed or silenced

2 Fam198a

Fam129a

3 Tmtc2

Cldn3

4 Sgta

Fcrl3

5 GAS2L3

6 GAS7 was luminal enriched.

7 Second messengers

8 Subtype specific PDEs and adenylyl Cyclases: look at survival by PDE type to determine if the PDE is
9 conferring survival benefit for the tumor

10 Genomic stability and DNA damage

11 These genes were among the least differentially expressed ("shared") as across the tumor transcriptomes
12 in luminal and non luminal subtypes, indicating they are either expressed at similar (small, modest or
13 large) quantities, or similarly silenced (equivalent diff exp because they are not present on the tumor at
appreciable levels).

14 Pms2p1

SLX1A/b

15 Sif1

Rad51d

16 CHEK1 and H2AFX appeared silenced in HER2/basal or activated in luminal

17 FEN1 was silenced in luminal or active in basal

18 Tp53bp1 was activated in luminal breast cancers

19 Transport and trafficking

20 Ap1s2

21 Ap2a1

Kdelr

22 Vps13D and Vps39

23 Channels and drug resistance

24 Luminal ABC-binding cassette genes

25 ABCG1

ABCC5

26 ABCD3

ABCC8

27 ABCA3

ABCA8

28 SIDT1

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Basal/HER2 subtype ABC-binding cassette genes

- ABCF1
- ABCE1
- ABCF2
- ABCC4
- ABCC10

MFSD4A was enriched in the basal subtype.

Mitochondria

Genes shared among subtype in differential expression

- TAMM41
- Atp5O
- Timm21

Kinase and phosphatase signaling

DYRK3 and MAP3K12 were subtype independent kinase targets.

MAP3K5 and MAP3K7 were luminal enriched.

STK36 and Wnk4 were basal and HER2 enriched.

Phosphatases

Basal

- PPP1CB
- PPP1R14C
- PTPN2
- PPM1G
- PPP2R1B
- PPP1R14B
- PPP2R3A

Luminal

- PPM1A
- INPP4B
- PTP4A2
- PPM1J
- PTPRB
- PPP6C
- DUSP28

1 Cytokine and morphogen signaling

2 HHAT was activated in luminal subtypes.

3 Wnt6 was expressed in the basal and HRR subtypes.

4 PDGFRB

5 VEGF-A

6 Homeobox and nuclear factor control of subtype: Subtype-specific gene expression

7 These genes provide information regarding cell of origin in breast cancer: do luminal and basal cancers
8 differ because they are products of transformation of different cells of the mammary duct (basal, luminal or
9 myoepithelial cells), or do they originate from a common cell of origin (e.g., stem cell in the mammary
10 duct).

11 Tns4 and Sept6 was shared expression by subtype: determine if those were Xist regulated,
12 subtype-specific genes to support a hypothesis that contends Xist functions in subtype selection; this can
13 also inform as to at which points of progression from founder clone, pre-cancer (ductal carcinoma in situ),
14 a defining selection event that results in generation of the molecular subtype, then progression to a
15 hormone receptor positive, HER2 expressing or triple negative primary tumor.

16 TBX3, GATA3, HOXC4 and PBX1, as well as FOXP1 and FOXA1, and ZEB1 were luminal enriched. Lhfp
17 was luminal enriched. TEF, CASZ1 and GLI3 were luminal enriched. SOX6 was luminal enriched. Tcf4 and
18 Tcf12 were luminal enriched, as was Lef1. Klf2 was luminal enriched. HOXC6, Hoxc9, Hoxd8 and HoxB2
19 were also luminal enriched (in addition to HOXC4). TBX3 and TBX5 were luminal enriched.

20 RARA and RORC were luminal enriched .

21 DNMT1 and TET3 were basal enriched or luminally silenced.

22 Luminal zinc fingers nuclear factors included ZNF4, ZNF703, ZNF500, ZNF740 and ZNF688.

23 Luminal epigenetic factors included CHD1, TDRD3 and ARID2 as well as CHD6, HDAC2 and METTL14,
24 in addition to KDM4B and KDM3B. EZH1 was modestly enriched in HR luminal subtype.

25 TCF3, FOXC1, HMGB3, KLF1, and DIEXF. FOXM1, FOXN1 and FOXC2 were basal and HER2 enriched.
26 BTF3L4 was enriched in basal and HER2, as was BCL11A and DBF4. Hmga1 and Hmgb2 were basal and
27 HER2 enriched. Sox10 and SOX11 was basal and HER3 enriched. Tcf19 was basal enriched, as was
28 Tcf7L1, TCF20 and Tcf15. Klf5 and Klf11 were basal and HER2 enriched. PAX6 was basal and HER2
enriched.

MBD6 and PHF19, ARID4A, and TAF5 were enriched in basal/HER2, as was EED and EZH2.

Basal/HER2 subtype zinc finger nuclear factors included ZPR1, ZNF292, ZNF22, ZNF750 and ZNF451.

1 Nutrient sensing and energy (PI3K/AKT)

2 TSC2, PIK3C3, TBC1D12, TBC1D9 and TBC1D17 were enriched in the luminal subtypes, as was
3 SLC39A6 and SLC7A8 and SLC16A6.

4 IGFBP4 was activated in the luminal subtypes.

5 TBC1D7 was enriched in basal subtypes as was TBC1D31 and TBC1D22B.

6 Genes that define polarity in tissues with basal and luminal orientation

7 BBS4 and BBS1 were enriched in luminal subtypes and may provide insight into timeframe of subtype
8 selection and cell of origin questions. BCAM, a gene whose description suggests basal cell expression,
9 was enriched in luminal types.

10 PLK4, an asymmetric cell division program gene, was silenced in luminal types relative to basal and
11 HER2, as was PLK1. Keratins are PAM50 component genes; KRT16 was enriched in basal HER2.

12 AGR2 and AGR3 were enriched in the luminal subtypes.

13 PARD6B and PARD6A were luminal subtype defining, while PARD3B was expressed in the basal and
14 HER2+ subtypes. PRICKLE

15 PCNX1 and PCNX4 were luminal enriched.

16 Other systems

17 CBR4, HTRA4 were enriched in luminal types, as was THRB.

18 CROT was luminal enriched.

19 Cell cycle

20 Cyclin J was enriched in basal and HER2 subtypes, as was CDK1.

21 CCNG2 was enriched in luminal subtypes.

22 CDK8 was basal and HER2 enriched.

23 Metabolism and redox

24 Glutaredoxins were enriched in basal and HER2 or silenced in luminal A/B.

25 IDNK was activated in luminal types

26 ME1 was activated in luminal subtypes.

27 Hacd3 was luminal enriched.

28 KDSR was enriched in luminal subtypes.

HDHD2 was luminal

FAAH was luminal enriched

D2HGDH was luminal enriched.

HAGH was luminal enriched.

IVD was luminal enriched.

1 FH, Fumarate hydratase was activated in basal and HER2 tumors.
2 HACD2 was basal enriched.
3 DLAT WAS basal enriched.
4 HMBD was basal enriched.
5 MDH1 was basal enriched.
6 MDH2 was basal enriched.
7 DHTDK1 was basal enriched.
8 Ubiquitin system in cancer
9 TRIM23 was activated in luminal subtypes
10 USP30 _____
11 The spindle and kinetochore
12 Kif16b, Kif12, Kif3A, Kif13b, and Kif16b and Kif5C are luminal subtype-specific.
13 Kif _____
14 Neurotrophic factors
15 ADRA2A was luminal enriched.
16 AMFR was also luminal enriched
17 MREG was enriched in the luminal subtype.
18 Adora2b was basal/HER2 enriched.
19 NMU was enriched in basal and HER2 subtype tumors.
20 MANF expression was modestly enriched in HER2/basal subtypes, as was NENF.
21 Pannexin 1 (PANX1) was luminal enriched.
22 Purinergic receptors P2RX4 was luminally enriched, while P2RX5 was modest enriched in HER2 and
23 basal subtypes.
24 Adenyl cyclase and cAMP: ADCY9 and aDCY6 were the neighed in the luminal subtype.
25 Glutamate receptors
26 GABA signaling
27 GABBR2 and GABP were luminal enriched
28 Histamine
Dopamine
Serotonin
HTR2B was luminal enriched.
HTR6 was basal enriched.
HTR4 was similarly expressed.

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Cholinergic

CHRNA2 and CHRNB2, which were both expressed similarly between subtype.
CHRNA5 was slightly biased towards basal expression.

Hormones (GH/gonadotropic/Thyroid/)

Neuropeptides

NPY1R was luminal enriched.
GPR and NPFF were luminal enriched.
NMB was basal enriched.

Shared neurotransmitter machinery

Chrb2

Matrix

Steroid signaling

Stard10 was luminal enriched.
AKR7A3 and CYB5R1 were luminal enriched.
SRD5A1 and DHCR7 were basal and HER2 enriched.
CYB5R4
SDR42E1 was basal enriched.
Hsd17b4 was luminal enriched

Proteasome

Luminal

PSMA5
PSMF1
PSMG4
PAAF1

Basal and HER2+

PSME4
PSMB2
PSMB4
PSMG1
PSMG4
PSMG3
PSMA7
PSMA2
PSMC2
PSMD12
PSMA4
PSMB6
PSMB5
PSMB7
PSMA7

1 PSME3
2 PSMC3
3 PSMG2

4 Xist RNP factors Or imprinting associated

5 ILF2 and ILF3 were enriched in the basal and HER2+ subtypes, as was BAZ1A.

6 MATN3 was enriched in the luminal subtypes
7 BAZ2B was luminal enriched.

8 DZIP3 was basal enriched.
9 ZIC1 was luminal enriched.
10 BRWD1 was luminal enriched.
11 Dazap1 was basal enriched, while Dazap2 was luminal enriched.

12 Nucleotide synthesis

13 MTHFR was luminal enriched
14 DHFR was basal and HER2 enriched

15 TK2 was luminal enriched.
16 RRM2 and TYMS were basal and HER2 enriched.

17 Other

18 KTN1 and AGTR1 was enriched in luminal subtypes.

19 ADM was basal and HER2 enriched.

20 CNRIP1 and GLRB was luminal enriched.

21 Metaxin and frataxin _____

22 Axon guidance

23 SEMA3C and PLXNDC1 were luminal enriched
24 Unc5b _____

25 Hippo signaling

26 YAP

27 TEAD1 was luminal enriched
28 TEAD4 and TEAD2 was basal enriched

TAZ was equivalently differentially expressed between subtype.

1 Regeneration and wound healing genes in molecular subtype
2 AREG in luminal
3 CILP1/2 in luminal
4 CRTAP and COMP in luminal
5 Asymmetric cell division
6 Aph1a: basal
7 Aph1b: luminal
8 MON2 in luminal
9 Polarity genes
10 Vangl1/2 and Vgll1 in basal
11 DLG5 in luminal
12 CROCC _____
13 Cell death
14 BIRC5 and BAIAP2L1 in basal and HER2
15 BCL2L12 and BCL2L13 in basal and HER2
16 BAX and BID in basal and HER2+
17 CFLAR in basal and HER,2+
18 DEDD in basal
19 BCL2A1 basal
20 BCL2 in luminal
21 Basal subtype TNF genes
22 TNFRSF10A and TNFRSF10A
23 TNFRSF21
24 Other Xist associated genes: UHRF1 in basal
25
26 Other genes
27 RNA-binding
28 PURA enriched in luminal
FUBP1 enriched in basal
PTBP3 in basal subtype
CIRBP enriched in luminal subtype

1 POLI in luminal subtype
2 U2AF1 in basal and HER2+
3 TIGD2 and PGBD5 in basal and HER2 subtypes

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5 Basal
6 Mad111
7 Mad112
8 Trip13

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10 Rif1
11 HELLS

12
13 Luminal
14 Trip11
15 Trip12

16
17 EME2: luminal
18 Cenpb: basal HER2
19 Suv39h2: basal

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21 Larp4b: basal
22 Ahnak: luminal

23
24 Cdy12: luminal
25 Pcbp2: luminal

26
27 CGGBP1: basal
28 Rad17: basal
BRCA2: basal

29 Discussion

30 We defined here the defining transcriptional differences in luminal versus basal and HER2+ non-luminal
31 subtypes breast cancer in humans. Whether these cancers arise from a common myoepithelial cell of
32 origin or arise from transformation of luminal versus basal mammary epithelial cells has not yet been
33 established. HER2 status as a function of subtype versus a separable component of luminal versus basal
34 subtypes is not yet understood.

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